

Violence to Women During Pregnancy: An Empirical Survey in the Rural Areas of District Saharanpur U.P.

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Abstract

Last decades saw the emergence of violence against women, and as a consequence government of India came up with yet a new Act, namely “**The Protection of Women From Domestic Violence Act, 2005**”. The distinctive features of this Act are unique and most likely to end this menace called Domestic Violence. This Act is the result of the women’s movement which succeeded in dragging this issue from ‘private’ to ‘public’ domain. This is a secular law, it is civil in nature. Again, this is a gender specific Act and an emergency law. Even the Act provides for appointment of ‘the Protection Officer’ and ‘Service Provider’. To achieve the objective of this endeavour to display how much violence is done in the pregnancy period in the rural areas of Saharanpur District. Women have been given single question threshold approach. Table 1.1 and Table 1.2 have been given where the occurrence of violence during pregnancy has been shown, and it has been inferred from the study that almost 67.6 percent women face physical and psychological violence during pregnancy and in almost 14.6 percent cases they need medical support due to grievous injuries. At the end, some suggestions have been given.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, the Protection Officer, the Service Provider.

Introduction

In designing the social order man manipulated his biological strengths and set aside privileges and power positions superior to woman for himself. Men’s superiority and women’s inferiority perpetuated throughout human history. Based on this inequality the social order that emerged is basically patriarchal social order.

Any challenge to male superiority or women’s attempt to expand their social space is subjected to control through violence. Violence against women has taken various forms like- rape, kidnapping and abduction, dowry death, murder, molestation, sexual harassment, torture both mental and physical etc. when violence against women is perpetuated by the members of the family it is termed as domestic violence.

In India and probably the world over domestic violence perpetrated against women by partners and close family members continues to remain a matter of silent suffering within the four walls of the home..... The phenomenon of intimate violence against women is typically identified as a private matter, made invisible by society and kept under wraps because of concerns of guilt, shame and secrecy. The norms that perpetuate silence and the stigma around domestic violence in family and community setting permeate the formal institutional response as well. (Nandita Bhalla and Anuradha Rajan, 2003)¹

Distinctive Characteristics of Domestic Violence

The display of negative emotions in the behavior by the members of a family while interacting with other members of the family is known as domestic violence. different types of aggression domestics violence involves:

- a. Individuals who have a continuing inter- personal relationship that can lead to repetitive violence, and
- b. The interpersonal relationship of attachment, sexual intimacy and dependence between marital partners.

The Extent of Domestic violence in India

It is difficult to estimate the extent of domestic violence in India. There are two basic problems which compound to the difficulty. Firstly, relates to the nature of domestic violence. It take place behind closed doors, is concealed from the public eye and is often unknown to anyone outside the immediate family, secondly, no governmental or non-governmental agency is made responsible to collect data on the issue. This results in the absence of macro level data.

Available evidences from the Crime Record Bureau indicate that domestic violence reigns rampant within Indian homes. Not only has this had the overall number of cases of crimes against women gone up in the past five years not only numbers of cases but these has been a dramatic increase in violence against women in the household² (Crimes in India, NCRB, Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of India)

The urgent need of India women for protection from domestic violence given rise to the specific law enactment which could combat to the social evil of domestic violence and it resulted in.

“The Protection of women from Domestic violence Act 2005” which come into force on 26 Oct. 2006.

Basic Features of Domestic Violence Act

The basic features of the Domestic violence Act 2005 may be displayed as below-

Force after Enactment

This Act is a product of women’s movement in India. Though the constitution of India recognizes and guarantees equal rights to women as individuals the state has hardly perceived and treated them as equals. It is rightly said that in India citizenship has for long been exclusively viewed as the domain of men. Women’s issues have always been dealt within the context of family and are therefore considered as “private”. The women’s movement made consistent efforts to drag this “private” to “public” domain. The women’s movement consider “private as political” tool of suppression by men.

Secular Law

The unique feature of the Act is that it is a secular law applicable on all uniformly irrespective of the family’s religious orientations. Thus, it is a step towards uniform law in the personal life of individuals. In India – marriage, family relations, divorce, inheritance of property are governed by the personal laws of all the communities, we have Hindu marriage law, Muslim marriage law etc. This Act is confined to women and the family and do not take religion in consideration.

Civil Nature

The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act is a civil law. Its aim is to provide protection, compensation and support to women victims of domestic violence. It is not intended to penalize the perpetrators of violence. The Act emphasizes domestic violence as an undesirable state but do not recognize violence as a criminal act. This Act only restraint the perpetrators but do not punish them for any commissioning of domestic violence.

Gender Specific Enactment

This Act is gender specific act not a gender natural act. It can be invoked by women only and the respondent is invariably a male member of the family.

An Emergency Law

This is an emergency law as she can take “stop violence” order immediately. The intention of the law is to give women a space free from violence, where she can evaluate her options and choose her future course of action. The law is in addition to other laws, a woman can take recourse to the other provisions for seeking the appropriate remedy later on.

Access to Justice as well as Support System

This act ensures a women access to the justice system as well as access to the support system. In the act “the protection officer” and “service providers” are inbuilt i.e. the act created these institutions. The protection officer is to serve as a link between the women and the court as well as enable her to access the support provided under the Act. The service providers provide necessary support to the woman, which she might require such as medical facilities, shelter home, schooling of children, legal support etc.

The Objectives of the Study

Through this objectives empirical study we are intended to point out the reality of the level of violence during the pregnancy of women weather they are exempt from rude of violent behavior during the critical and sensitive period of pregnancy.

Research Methodology

For the present survey data were collected from ten villages from the district of Saharanpur. Saharanpur district is situated in the West Uttar Pradesh. It border with Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh, and Haryana. This

district is the hometown of the research hence a convenient sampling it was sampled out. The other reason for its selection is that it represents the mixed culture or Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, and Haryana and culture of the Hindu heartland. There is much influence of urban area as well as Muslim society on the rural masses.

Sampling the Villages

The selection of the Villages was guided with the size consideration the village. It was thought that villages with approximately 400 to 600 households be sampled out for survey. Another consideration was that the study should concentrate on Hindu population only as personal Laws are different for each religious community. Caste composition of the villages was also considered, we included two villages each with dominant caste Rajput. Gujjar, Saini, scheduled castes and mixed population. With these consideration following villages were included for survey.

1. Naurangpur
2. Kapoori Govindpur
3. Meerpur Mohanpur
4. Khajoorwala
5. Bhalaswa Isapur @ Beri Bhalsawa
6. Khajoori Akbarpur
7. Paharpur
8. Chondaheri
9. Majhaul Jabardastpur
10. Ramdaspur @ Nagal

The present survey relied on the Demographic and Health Survey module as developed in 1988-90 for data collection. The present survey developed an interview schedule incorporation the above module with certain culturally necessary modification. The DHS module is based on Conflict Tactics Scale (CTS) which was developed by sociologist Murray Straus in the 1970s. This is a refined version of the single – question threshold approach. In single question threshold approach respondent is asked a single question to determine whether she has ever experienced violence. Women who give a positive response are then asked more questions, such as who the perpetrator was/is. If they give a negative answer no follow up questions are asked. Thus, the women is given only one chance to disclose the occurrence of violence. In CTS approach include about 15 acts of physical and psychological violence. If the respondent affirms that any one of the specified acts or out comes has taken place, she is considered to have experienced violence. Thus it gives respondent multiple opportunities to disclose the experience of violence.

Table 1.1
Occurrence of violence during pregnancy among the sampled households

Name of Village	Violent Households	Violence During Pregnancy
Naurangpur	108	90
	100	83.33
Kapoori Govindpur	93	79
	100	84.94
Meerpur Mohanpur	113	92
	100	81.41
Khajoorwala	87	38
	100	43.67
Bhalaswa Isapur	122	67
	100	54.91
Khajoori Akbarpur	104	52
	100	50.00
Paharpur	113	84
	100	74.33
Chondaheri	86	65
	100	75.58
Majhaul Jabardastpur	107	68
	100	63.55
Nagal	96	61

	100	63.54
	1029	696
Total	100	67.60

Table 1.2
Occurrence of violence resulting in the need for Medical Support for Women

Name of Village	Violent Households	Violence During pregnancy
Naurangpur	86	13
	100	15.11
Kapoori Govindpur	76	07
	100	9.21
Meerpur Mohanpur	86	08
	100	9.30
Khajoorwala	55	04
	100	7.27
Bhalaswa Isapur	80	11
	100	13.75
Khajoori Akbarpur	85	12
	100	14.11
Paharpur	95	25
	100	26.21
Chondaheri	68	13
	100	19.11
Majhaul Jabardastpur	85	12
	100	14.11
Nagal	72	10
	100	13.88
Total	788	115
	100	14.60

Analysis of Data

Table 1.1 demonstrates the occurrence of incidences of violence during pregnancy in the violent households. The data indicates that 67.6 percent women had to face physical and psychological violence during pregnancy also. It points out the insensitivity of their husbands towards the special care of women during those crucial days.

Table 1.2 shows the occurrence of violence resulting in the need of medical support for victim women. Out of 788 women who faced physical violence 14.6 per cent needed medical support since they were beaten brutally some of them received head injuries, profound bleeding or stomach upset because of the blows on the abdomen. Hair pulling twisting of arms, slapping on the face, blows on the abdomen, scratching by nails around eh breast and pelvic region are common incidence of violence.

Conclusion

It is inferred from the study that almost 67.6 percent women face physical and psychological violence even during pregnancy and in almost 14.6 percent cases they need medical support due to grievous injuries.

Suggestions

Domestic violence free society in the world is not impossible; however, there are several challenges as the researcher felt while observing/ dealing with the experiences of functionaries and victims of the domestic violence. On the basis of this endeavour some important suggestions are put forward for making improvement in infrastructure and attitude to control domestic violence as follows-

Appointment of Protection Officer

It is recommended that – There should be appointment of Protection Officer with exclusive charge as protection officer. He/She should be bear requisite academic as well as professional qualification and experience as the researcher has found lack of appointment of full time Protection officers.

Registration of Service Provider

Service providers are next to protection officers and they are close and primary helping hand to the protection officer. The researcher has realized lack of service providers as a big obstacle in efficient working of PWDVA.

Medical facilities and Shelter Homes

Medical facilities and shelter homes are the first port of call for women who receive injuries due to domestic violence. There is a shelter home at Fatehpur about 30km. far from the district head quarter named "Nari Niketan Evam Mahila Sudhar Grah" that is always in crisis of funds and the living circumstances there are very poor and measurable.

So it is suggested and highly recommended to -

- Arrange the shelter home at district head quarter at the locality which may be accessible to the aggrieved person at any time.
- The shelter home should be free from the formalities of documentations and direction of the court as these things may be completed later on. The sole objective of these shelter homes should be to provide immediate shelter to the aggrieved person.
- There should be a medical facility centre attached with the shelter home where the aggrieved person may receive physical as well as psychological treatment.

Funds Allocation

The researcher is shocked to know that Govt. has not committed any resources for implementation of the Act and the functionaries are suffering badly due to lack of funds.

Sensitizing and Training the Stakeholders

The stakeholders must be trained and sensitized properly to perform their duty with honesty and efficiency having gender sensitive approach towards victims of domestic violence.

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